

A MODEL FOR THE DECONSOLIDATION PHENOMENON IN INDUCTION HEATING OF THERMOPLASTIC RESIN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the causes of deconsolidation encountered in post processing of thermoplastic resin composites. The deconsolidation of APC-2 composite in uniform temperature fields was studied experimentally. No deconsolidation was observed after prolonged heating up to 420°C. The results suggest that for APC-2 composite the fiber elastic deformation, the void growth and the residual stresses are not the direct cause for deconsolidation. The deconsolidation observed during welding processes may be caused by the thermal stresses in nonuniform temperature fields. A one dimensional thermal buckling model is proposed to explain the deconsolidation phenomenon in induction heating of APC-2 composite laminates.

Keywords: deconsolidation, delamination, welding, thermoplastic composites

1. INTRODUCTION

The deconsolidation is defined as the structural disintegration of originally consolidated composite panels. In laminated composite structures, deconsolidation can be void formation, delamination, buckling and other types of physical degradation. The problem of deconsolidation is of great concern in post processing of thermoplastic composites. Benefited by the fusible nature of thermoplastic resins, thermoplastic composites can be formed, joined and repaired by local melting and reconsolidation processes. However, such processes may cause deconsolidation of the composite panels if the consolidation pressure is not sufficiently high. This problem has been encountered in welding and repair practices.

The nature of the deconsolidation, so far, is not clearly understood. It has been suggested that the elastic energy of the fibers and the residual stresses may be the cause of deconsolidation [1-3]. These factors seem to be important in processes where the temperature distribution is uniform. On the other hand the thermal stresses induced by nonuniform heating may play a more decisive role in deconsolidation encountered in welding processing. This study is aimed at understanding the deconsolidation phenomenon. In particular, the present paper discusses the factors causing deconsolidation in induction heating process. A one dimensional thermal buckling model is proposed to explain the deconsolidation phenomenon in induction heating of thermoplastic resin composites. The material studied is APC-2 composite.

2. DECONSOLIDATION IN UNIFORM TEMPERATURE FIELDS

2.1. Laminate preparation

The experiments were conducted both on the unidirectional laminate and on the cross-ply laminate. The unidirectional laminate is free from the residual stresses and thus the research can be focused at

the role of elastic energy of the fibers whereas the cross-ply laminate may reveal the role of residual stresses.

Four 24-ply unidirectional laminates and one cross-ply laminate were molded from APC-2 composite prepreg using a compression press with the same temperature cycle but different pressures. The mold was made of steel with a molding dimension of 6x6 inch. The wall thickness of the mold is one inch. Prepreg lay-up was put into the mold and then was pressed in the preheated press under a low pressure. When the temperature of the inside wall of the mold reached 380°C, a high pressure (consolidation pressure) was applied. The temperature was maintained at 380°C for 15 minutes and then cooled at 15°C/min. The consolidation pressure was maintained through the cooling process. The applied consolidation pressure and the resulted laminate thickness are given in Table 1 which shows a steady loss of the degree of consolidation with decreasing pressure. The consolidated composite panels were sectioned for microscopic examination. The two panels consolidated at 0.69 MPa apparently are free of voids while other three panels display interply voids.

2.2. Deconsolidation treatment

The deconsolidation treatments were conducted in a high temperature oven. Small samples of 6x18 mm were cut from the panels. One edge of the sample was polished for microscopic inspection. The samples were sandwiched between two aluminium plates of 3 mm thickness. The possible transverse fiber flow was damped by two aluminium strips of 3 mm thickness. The whole set up was then put into the oven and placed between two blocks of steel of 10 mm thickness which had reached the desired temperature in the oven. The load produced by the weight of the steel block and the aluminium plate on the top of the samples was about 0.02 MPa which was the only pressure applied during the deconsolidation tests. The air temperature of the oven was measured by a thermocouple during deconsolidation process. It is assumed to be the equilibrium temperature of the samples in this study.

The samples were heated at different temperatures with various time durations. After heating, the whole sample sandwich was taken out the oven and cooled in air. Without the steel blocks, such a treatment has caused warpage of the samples due to nonuniform cooling through the thickness.

2.3 Results and discussion

After each deconsolidation treatment, the samples were examined by microscopic inspection and by measuring the laminate thickness. The first treatment was at 370°C for 10 minutes. Such a treatment did not cause any distinguishable change in the cross section views as compared with the photographs taken on the samples as molded. The interply voids originally formed during consolidation in the samples from panels No.2 to No.4 remained the same size. The samples were then treated at 380°C for 10 minutes and examined again with the microscope. At this stage, the voids formed during the consolidation remained the same size but numerous new voids appeared at the resin rich areas both between plies and within plies. The larger the resin rich area, the larger the lately formed voids. But these voids were only holes at the surface layer formed by resin loss from free surfaces since they can be removed by polishing. It was observed that after polishing the samples from panel No.1 displayed a void free appearance as that before the deconsolidation treatment. The resin flow traces at the surfaces of treated samples provide additional evidence for the cause of new voids, as can be seen in Figure 1. The phenomenon of surface voids was observed on the samples that underwent deconsolidation treatments at higher temperatures and longer duration. The results on the laminate thickness are summarized in Table 2. The laminate thickness remains unchanged even for the most severe treatment at 420°C for 60 minutes. Limited results on the short beam shear strength show that the deconsolidation treatment does not have any noticeable effect on the short beam values after 420°C/20 minute deconsolidation treatment. The above results lead to the conclusion that in uniform temperature field APC-2 unidirectional laminate does not deconsolidate.

Deconsolidation tests were also made on cross-ply laminate. A sample from a 16-ply cross-ply laminate was put into the oven at 400°C for 20 minutes. The cross section views of the sample before and after the deconsolidation are shown in Figure 2. As can be seen in Figure 2b, the

voids formed due to resin flow appear in the plies where fibers are perpendicular to the free surface. Resin flow might have occurred at the plies where fibers are parallel to the free surfaces as revealed by the difference in focus depth for the plies with different fiber orientations. The average ply thickness remained unchanged. The preliminary results on [0/90] laminate negate the suggestion that the residual stresses are the cause of deconsolidation in APC-2 composite.

It is worth noting that the present results on APC-2 composite do not agree with the results on the J-polymer/graphite composite [1,2]. It was reported that heating without pressure can result in a significant thickening and a loss of the short beam shear strength of J-polymer composite. The elastic energy stored in the fibers is suggested to be the cause of deconsolidation [1,3]. The discrepancy in deconsolidation behaviour between APC-2 and J-polymer composite might be due to the interfacial adhesion. The carbon fiber in APC-2 is well wetted by PEEK resin and thereby the capillary force acting between the fibers is likely much stronger and may offset the spring back force of the fibers.

Our results suggest that neither elastic energy in the fibers nor the residual stresses can cause deconsolidation of APC-2 composite in uniform temperature fields. The deconsolidation problem encountered in welding of APC-2 composite thus should be attributed to additional factors and the most likely factor is the thermal stresses induced by nonuniform temperature fields in welding processes.

3. DECONSOLIDATION IN NONUNIFORM TEMPERATURE FIELDS

3.1. Nonuniform temperature field in induction heating

In induction heating, eddy current is induced within the work piece and heat is generated by the resistive heating of the work piece. But the eddy current tends to follow a loop mirroring the induction coil. On the other hand, the thermal conductivity of the composites is relatively low. This results in a nonuniform heating pattern in composite panels. A pancake shaped coil was found to result in a circular annulus heating pattern over the composite panels [5,6]. The heat intensity as a function of the radius distance in a thin work piece [6] is shown in Figure 3.

The temperature field in the work piece has a radial distribution similar to that of heat intensity in Figure 3. The highest temperature is found at a radius distance close to $r=R$ (R is the radius of the coil) and the heating effect becomes negligible at a radius distance $r \geq 2R$ and at $r \rightarrow 0$. Thus a great temperature gradient is present along the radial direction. The thermal expansion in the hot annulus is restricted by the surrounding cold zone which creates a radially compressive stress. This may cause thermal buckling of the work piece. In the case of composite laminate, sub-laminate buckling is likely to occur.

3.2. One dimensional analysis

The in-plane temperature distribution in the work piece can be considered to be one dimensional along the radial direction and thus the stress analysis can be reduced to one dimensional. The further simplification reduces the problem to a clamped beam element subjected to a symmetric temperature distribution over the length of the beam, as schematically shown in Figure 4. The beam is made of a laminate [0/90]s and the fiber in [0] layer is parallel to the beam axis.

If a symmetric and linear temperature distribution as shown in Figure 4 is assumed, then the total thermal deformation is

$$\Delta l_T = 2\alpha^0(T_{\max}-T_0)L \int_0^L (L-l) dl = \alpha^0 L(T_{\max}-T_0) \quad (1)$$

where L is the half length of the beam; α^0 is the equivalent thermal expansion coefficient along the beam axis; T_{\max} is the temperature at $l=0$ and T_0 is the temperature at $l=L$.

α^0 can be calculated according to the classic laminate theory [8]. For [0/90]s laminate:

$$\alpha_1^0 = \frac{(E_1 + \nu_{12}E_2)\alpha_1 + (E_2 + \nu_{12}E_1)\alpha_2}{E_1 + E_2 + 2\nu_{12}E_2} \quad (2)$$

where E_1 and E_2 are the elastic moduli in the fiber and transverse directions; α_1 and α_2 are the coefficients of expansion in the fiber and transverse directions; and ν_{12} is the Poisson's ratio. The above thermoelastic properties are temperature dependent. The values used in calculation (following [5]) and the calculated α^0 values are summarized in Table 3.

Restricted by the clamped boundary, such a thermal expansion creates a thermal strain in the beam:

$$\epsilon_T = -\alpha^0(T_{\max} - T_0)/2 \quad (3)$$

and therefore the thermal stress in the [0] layer is

$$\sigma_T^{[0]} = -Q^{[0]} \epsilon_T \approx -\alpha^0 E_1 (T_{\max} - T_0)/2 \quad (4)$$

According to (4), heating from 20°C to 420°C results in a compressive thermal stress of 45.6 MPa in the fiber direction. Furthermore, due to the boundary restraint the residual stresses from the previous consolidation cannot be released by heating. The residual stress in the fiber direction in [0/90]_s laminate is compressive, about 42 MPa [7]. This leads to an estimated maximum compressive stress of 88 MPa along the fiber direction in the [0] layer.

The welding process requires that $T_{\max} > T_m$ where T_m is the melting point of the matrix resin. In the melting zone, however, the matrix stiffness degrades drastically and the [0] layer is no longer supported by the [90] layer. The compressive stress in the [0] layer may cause sub-laminate buckling in the melting zone. Buckling may occur at $T < T_m$ as far as the restriction of the [90] layer becomes negligible. Therefore the stress free temperature $T_{sf} = 310^\circ\text{C}$ [7] was chosen as the lower limit for buckling zone. The [0] layer within the stress free zone may be considered as an Euler beam with a length confined by the zone, as shown in Figure 4. For the restricted end condition, the critical buckling stress is predicted by

$$\sigma_C = -\pi^2(t/l)^2 E_1/12 \quad (5)$$

where t is the thickness of the [0] layer and l is the half length of the stress free zone.

$$l = L(T_{\max} - T_{sf}) / (T_{\max} - T_0) \quad (6)$$

for linear temperature distribution. Figure 5 plots the critical buckling stress σ_C as a function of t/l .

A critical value of $l/t = 35$ is found for $\sigma_C = 88$ MPa. Introducing $l/t \leq 35$ into (6) leads to:

$$T_{\max} - T_{sf} \leq 35 T_L \quad (7)$$

where T_L is the temperature gradient along the beam axis.

The relationship between the T_{\max} , T_L and the onset of buckling predicted by (7) is shown in Figure 6. The shaded area indicates the buckling free processing zone. A thicker [0] layer increases the maximum allowable processing temperature for the same size of the melting zone.

Buckling may be prevented by transversely applied pressure. The critical pressure required to prevent buckling is estimated by assuming that the deflection of the Euler beam caused by the transverse pressure offsets the deflection caused by thermal buckling. The buckling deflection of the Euler beam δ may be approximated by the amount of thermal expansion of the beam as $\Delta l_T = (\pi\delta)^2/8l$. For the restricted end condition, the required pressure for the case of an uniformly distributed load is

$$P = \frac{4E_b(t/l)^3(T_{\max} - T_0)\sqrt{2\alpha^0/(T_{\max} - T_{sf})}}{\pi} \quad (8)$$

and for the case of a concentrated load is

$$P = \frac{2E_b(t/l)^3(T_{\max} - T_0)\sqrt{2\alpha^0/(T_{\max} - T_{sf})}}{\pi} \quad (9)$$

where E_b is the flexural modulus in the fiber direction, $E_b=120$ GPa for APC-2. The uniformly distributed load is equivalent to applying pressure by a flexural bag such as vacuum bagging while the concentrated load is equivalent to applying pressure with a rigid molding plate. It can be seen that a rigid mold is as much as two times more efficient than a flexural bag. The transverse pressure, if sufficiently high, will press the center of the bowing beam back to the undeformed position, creating two new beams-each with a span and a deflection being a half of that of the original beam. A higher pressure is thus needed for further compression. This follows the theory of elastic fiber deformation by Gutowski [3]. For a n-fold beam, relation (9) becomes:

$$P = \frac{2E_b}{\pi} \left(\frac{2^{n-1}t}{l} \right)^3 (T_{\max} - T_0) \sqrt{2\alpha^0 / (T_{\max} - T_{sf})} \quad (10)$$

Figure 7 shows the P values versus l/t calculated by relation (10) for several typical processing conditions.

3.3 Results and Discussion

The one dimensional model can qualitatively predict the buckling phenomenon encountered in induction heating of APC-2 composite. It was found that heating without pressure causes a circular annular shaped buckling zone on cross-ply laminates, corresponding to the observed heating pattern. Heating with vacuum bagging can restore the buckled plate into its original flat shape but delamination remains in a smaller scale which can be detected by ultrasonic C-scan. A rigid molding plate under the bagging film is indeed more efficient to reduce the scale of delamination. The quantitative verification of the model requires further experiments.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The deconsolidation of APC-2 composite laminates in uniform temperature fields was studied experimentally. It was observed that (1) the voids formed from the consolidation stage apparently do not affect the deconsolidation; (2) under uniform heating and cooling conditions, there is no measurable change in laminate thickness for deconsolidation treatment up to 420°C/60 minutes under a low pressure of 0.02 MPa; (3) resin flow occurs when heated at above 380°C which left holes on free surfaces in resin rich areas; (4) the short beam shear strength remains unchanged after 420°C/20 minute deconsolidation treatment. The above results suggest that in uniform temperature fields the balanced APC-2 composite laminates do not deconsolidate and thereby neither the elastic energy in the fibers nor the void growth is the direct cause for the deconsolidation encountered in welding APC-2 composite. In uniform temperature fields the residual stresses do not cause deconsolidation.

The thermal stresses are suggested to be the cause for the delamination type of deconsolidation in nonuniform temperature fields. A one dimensional thermal buckling model is proposed to explain the deconsolidation encountered during induction heating of thermoplastic composites. The model qualitatively predicts the delamination phenomenon.

5. REFERENCES

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TABLE 1 CONSOLIDATION PRESSURE AND THE LAMINATE THICKNESS

Panel No.	Consolidation Pressure MPa (psi)	24-ply Unidirectional laminate thickness (mm)
1. [0] ₂₄	0.69 (100)	3.04 (0.127/ply)
2. [0] ₂₄	0.34 (50)	3.17 (0.130/ply)
3. [0] ₂₄	0.19 (28)	3.23 (0.135/ply)
4. [0] ₂₄	0.08 (12)	3.27 (0.138/ply)
5. [0/90] _{8s}	0.69 (100)	2.00 (0.125/ply)

TABLE 2 DECONSOLIDATION TREATMENT AND THE LAMINATE THICKNESS

Panel No.	Deconsolidation treatment (T°C/min)	Laminate thickness (mm)
1	as molded	0.127/ply
	380/15	0.127/ply
	400/20	0.127/ply
	420/20	0.127/ply
	420/60	0.127/ply
2	as molded	0.130/ply
	380/15	0.130/ply
3	as molded	0.135/ply
	380/10	0.135/ply
4	as molded	0.137/ply
	380/10	0.137/ply
5	as molded	0.125/ply
	400/20	0.125/ply

TABLE 3 THERMOELASTIC PROPERTIES OF APC-2

temperature range (°C)	E ₁ (GPa)	E ₂ (GPa)	ν_{12}	α_1 ($\mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$)	α_2 ($\mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$)	α^0 ([0/90] _s) ($\mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$)
20-143	134	8.9	0.31	0.6	29.1	3.1
143-300	134	1.0	0.5	0.6	80.0	1.5
above 400	134	0.1	0.5	0.6	80.0	0.6

Figure 1. The cross section view of a $[0]_{24}$ sample after heated at 380°C for 10 minutes under a slight pressure of 0.02 MPa. The sample was molded under 0.69 MPa.

Figure 2. The cross section views of a $[0/90]_{88}$ sample before and after deconsolidation test. The sample was molded under 0.69 MPa. a) as molded; b) after heated at 400°C for 20 minutes under a slight pressure of 0.02 MPa.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. The calculated heat intensity distribution in a thin isotropic work piece lying parallel to a pancake shaped induction coil. Curves 1,2,3 and 4 correspond to $z/R = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$, respectively, where z is the distance between the work piece and the coil and R is the radius of the outmost ring of the coil.

Figure 4. One dimensional thermal buckling model: the beam element and the temperature distribution over the beam.

Figure 5. The critical buckling stress versus the ratio of the length of the stress free zone to the thickness of the [0] layer.

Figure 6. The predicted buckling free processing zone.

Figure 7. The predicted welding pressure versus the ratio of the delamination size to the thickness of the [0] layer.